

NATIONAL-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONCEPT OF "DEATH" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, it is explained that the expression of units representing the concept of "death" is widely used in phraseological units, communication and other language tools. One of the bases of our scientific article is phraseological units and the role of euphemisms in softening them and conveying them to people's hearts. We highlighted and proved with examples the types of phraseological units and euphemisms between representatives of English culture and Muslim representatives.

Keywords: Phraseological units, euphemisms, scientific concept, linguistics, proverbs and phrases.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНО-КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОНЦЕПТА «СМЕРТЬ» В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМУ ЯЗЫКАХ

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Аннотация: В данной статье объясняется, что выражение единиц, репрезентирующих концепт «смерть», широко используется во фразеологизмах, средствах общения и других языковых средствах. Одной из основ нашей научной статьи являются фразеологизмы и роль эвфемизмов в

их смягчении и донесении до сердца людей. Мы выделили и доказали примерами типы фразеологизмов и эвфемизмов между представителями английской культуры и представителями мусульман.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, эвфемизмы, научное понятие, языкознание, пословицы и выражения.

While studying the field of concepts in different systematic languages in linguistics, we set ourselves the goal of revealing that the concept of "death" is also expressed by phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages. In all languages, as a rule, phraseological units make up the largest part of the cultural linguistic wealth of the peoples who speak these languages. These units preserve the world view of humanity, its own characteristics and reveal it to us linguists. Phraseological units have been of interest to linguists since the beginning of the 20th century as special types of language, and this combination of words has become the main goal and task of research. For the first time, in the 20s of the 20th century, the Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov independently divided phraseology into a separate section in linguistics and aims to study phraseological units in speech activity; it clarifies the science and the volume of phraseology, their object of study. That is, V.V. Vinogradov recognizes phraseological units as the basis of phraseology in speech activity. The well-known Russian linguist, specialist in English phraseology A.V. Kunin defines phraseology as follows: "Phraseology is the treasure of language. Phraseology reflects the history, culture and lifestyle of the people. Phraseology often has a national character." According to the scientist, the object of study of phraseology is stable combinations with complex semantics. When determining the status of these stable compounds in the language, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that they are partially or completely idiomatic in nature. Phraseological combinations are defined by experts as lexical complexes with special semantics. Phraseological units are distinguished from other language tools by their completeness, advantages in use, and conciseness. Expressed as a language unit, they serve to increase the level of speech effectiveness. Famous

Uzbek linguists Sh.Rakhmatullayev, M.Abdurakhimov, A.Ye.Mamatov, B.Yuldashev, M.H.Halikova, Sh.Abdullayev and G.Ergasheva also contributed to the study of phraseology. They applied their scientific and theoretical research and practical results on "phraseological units" to linguistics. According to A. Mamatov, "Phraseological units are lexical-semantic units made up of words or word combinations with their composition, and represent a generalized lexical meaning." There are problems of translation of phraseological units, among other units, and they always attract the attention of linguists L.S. came R. Fayzullayeva, a linguist, put forward the idea that "phraseology reflects the rich historical experience of the people, many views of people's work, life and culture." When we study the units representing the concept of "death" in different systematic languages, we can see that the majority of these units are phraseological units and reflect national and cultural views. Below we will explain the word combinations of units representing "death" in English and Uzbek languages and their national-cultural views.

There are also phraseological units, proverbs, proverbs used in the English language that mean "death", and we can see that they are used in their own sense and figuratively.

For example: phraseological units used in the English language in their own sense and figuratively:

Die away - "The last notes died away and therefore the audience burst into applause".

Die back - "The plant dies lower back in the winter".

Die down - "It was on the front pages of all the papers for many days, however the interest bit by bit died down".

Die for - "I'm dying for the weekend- this week' has been thus hard".

Die out - "Most of the elm trees in the GB died off once elm tree malady arrived".

Die on - "My computer died on American state the night before I had to submit my paper".

Die out - "Some scientists say that the dinosaurs died out as soon as an extraterrestrial item hit the arena and induced a nuclear winter".

Die happy - "If you retain fighting together with your mother now, she would possibly ultimately die laughing by taking you out of her will."

Passing on - "Another, a bearded Islamist, expressed his hope that man Chaudhry would fleetly pass a death on Mr Musharraf".

Dying out - "Dying, it turns out, is difficult business".

Feat out – "Jim smith would match him into th e new system while not leaving out duffy".

Die drop - "They'd to figure it out, and if she created like to him tonight, she'd cave in for sure".

Break down - "If a gadget or an automobile breaks down, it stops working."

Humans have been created so that phraseological units are widely used both in communication and in other language tools. One of the foundations of our scientific research is phraseological units and the role of euphemisms in softening them and conveying them to people's hearts. From time immemorial, the heart and value of people have been glorified, and euphemisms are a clear expression of these values. Telling the dead people about their death with soft and warm words will help even a little to the heavy separation that brings to people's hearts. We highlighted and proved with examples the types of phraseological units and euphemisms between representatives of English culture and Muslim representatives.

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